

FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCIES OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN COOPERATION WITH PARENTS

Kudyarova Artikgul

Student of the Faculty of primary education of
The Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12781341>

Abstract. In this thesis, the important factors related to speech development, speech competences, in particular, the linguistic and pedagogical features of improving students' speech competences in primary education mother tongue classes are analyzed.

Key words: written speech, communicative competence, correct pronunciation, vocabulary, literacy, work on the text.

INTRODUCTION

The work of developing students' speech begins when they go to the first grade. Speech skills are formed as a result of working in all sections of grammar to form and develop speech. Speech skills include concise, simple, and fluent speech: teaching students correct pronunciation and vocabulary development are the primary tasks.

Speech is a product of human thought and consciousness, and it is considered the main means of communication and a direct expression of human thinking and worldview. In this respect, speech development fully reflects the development of a person as a person. The formation and improvement of human spirituality is manifested in his speech as a whole. The fact that language (speech) has a strong influence, firstly, on the development of mental abilities in a person, and secondly, on its direct emotional, educational, and spiritual aspects, is part of the series of facts recognized in science. However, it is not correct to contradict them. The social, artistic and aesthetic functions of the language fulfill their tasks not at the expense of mutual negation, but at the expense of mutual cooperation and integrity.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Although human speech is formed and improved at birth, there is a need to develop it. This is done directly in the educational process. In particular, mother tongue education, as a special science dealing with the development of speech, occupies an important place in this regard.

Cultivating students' speech means teaching them the literary language of their people. Accustoming them to speak according to the pronunciation standards of the literary language is considered the main goal of speech cultivation.

Pupils develop the skills to increase vocabulary, master the standards of literary language, the pronunciation of each word that is new for the pupil, and the ability to convey the idea to the listener (others) orally and in writing. is considered the main task of mother tongue teaching.

The main goal of teaching mother tongue in modern education is: "a student who expresses his opinion correctly and fluently verbally and in writing, who has developed a culture of reading, who can think independently and creatively, who understands the opinion of others - communication and speech culture is the development of a person who has

developed ". Achieving this goal is directly related to the development of students' speech competence.

RESULTS

It is known that speech competence is the ability of students to apply knowledge, skills and abilities specific to oral and written speech in practice.

According to Professor B. Tokhliev: "under the concept of speech competence, the ability to speak correctly, quickly and vividly in the process of speech in the form of dialogue and monologue, to understand the spoken and read speech in a practical way Comprehension skills are imagined, the ability to understand speech patterns in any functional style.

Improvement of these competencies in students is considered one of the urgent tasks facing today's modern pedagogy, mother tongue teaching methodology, and this, in turn, is of great importance in the development of basic communicative competence (ability to engage in communication) in students.

Determining speech defects in the development of speech competences is also methodologically important. They are:

- local dialect or family influence;
- style of speaking, influence of "street language";
- ignoring students' oral speech at school;
- the presence of abnormal defects in the organs of speech: inability to pronounce "r",

such as tongue stiffness.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The important task of a school teacher is to recognize, eliminate and prevent these defects in time.

In primary education, it is advisable to develop the speech competence of students in the following directions [4]:

1. To produce perfect literacy of students based on the current alphabet.
2. To ensure that the standards of the literary language are mastered.
3. Enriching students' speech with vocabulary and grammatical construction.
4. Teaching different forms of speech activity.
5. To achieve students' oral and written speech literacy.
6. A special approach to the improvement of speech competences in the formation of linguistic competences;
7. Organization of each lesson based on the requirements of advanced pedagogical technology.
8. Systematic use of didactic games that include students' activity, cooperation, and individuality.

Formation and development of speech types is carried out separately in the educational process. However, it is appropriate to pay attention to their joint development. This requires a high level of intensity in alternating oral and written tasks. It is necessary to create conditions for pupils to encourage verbal expression of their thoughts, and verbal expression to be based on careful thought. Experts recommend developing them holistically as the most rational way to do this. Mastery of speaking and writing relies on listening and reading. On this basis, the competences of expressing oral and written opinions are formed in students. Its practical appearance is manifested in speaking and writing. Of course, each type of speech has its own competencies [5].

In primary education mother tongue classes, all sections of the language have ample opportunity to develop speaking ability.

For example: in the study of "phonetics" by changing a certain sound in a word, creating consonants, words, as well as rhyming words from suffixes, making words that rhyme, their vocabulary Working on nouns and meaning groups increases the student's vocabulary and develops his speaking skills.

"Lexicology" is the most important department in improving speech competences. When studying this section, distinguish between the original and figurative meaning of the word, work on polysemous, cognate, nested, cognate, antonymous, paronymous words. serves to increase and enrich the student's vocabulary, to form speech culture. Yoshavlod cultivates pride in his mother tongue, love, attention and respect for it.

Grammatical concepts: preliminary topics related to morphology (word groups) and syntax (word combinations, sentence structure), the processes of working on the text also significantly contribute to improving the speaking competence of primary school students. Also, in the development of students' oral and written speech, reading small passages, expressive reading, mastering the content, telling stories, composing texts, and types of written work: dictation, narration, and essays are also effective. have

CONCLUSIONS

The organization of all these processes on the basis of modern educational technologies, interactive methods, and didactic games has an important practical and effective position in achieving the goal of mother tongue education and speech literacy.

References:

1. Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Republican Education Center. State educational standard and curricula of continuous education in the subject of mother tongue. -T., 2017.
2. ЕРМАТОВА, Р. О. (2018). УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВРЕМЕННЫМ УЧЕНИЕМ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОБУЧЕНИЕМ ИНВАЛИДЫ. Наука среди нас, (7), 85-88.
3. Ermatova, R. O. (2018). ADVANTAGES OF THE TECHNIQUE "WHAT/HOW/WHY OUTLINES" IN DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS. Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук, (6), 69-71.
4. Utegenova, S., & Rozumova, D. (2024). DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING TAX AUDIT. Modern Science and Research, 3(6).
5. Utegenova, S., & Mirzabaeva, U. (2024). TODAY'S IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF AUDIT ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 4(6), 93-95.
6. Utegenova, S., & Oralbaeva, F. (2024). O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotiga xorijiy investitsiyalar oqimini oshirishda mamlakatning investitsion muhiti jozibadorligini oshirish. Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана, 1(6), 131-134.
7. Khasanova, S., Akisheva, N., & Zholayeva, M. (2023). Methodological aspects of tax planning in the context of sustainable development. Revista Gestão & Tecnologia, 23(3), 286-298.
8. Маматқулов, Б. М., & Нематов, А. А. (2021). Ўзбекистон Республикаси аҳолиси орасида COVID-19 тарқалишининг хусусиятлари.

9. Abdullayeva, N. (2023). AHMAD YASSAWI SECT: THE ISSUE OF ZIKR AND THE STATUS OF ZAKIR. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(5), 438-440.
10. Bazarov, S. (2024). JURNALIST VA BLOGERLAR NUTQI ETIKASI. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 3(1), 36-39.
11. Norqulovich, S. H. (2023, October). NURILLO CHORINING BADIY ASARLARIDA MILLIY KOLORITGA XOS KO 'RINISHLAR NUTQIY JIHATDAN IFODALANISHI. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 25-29).
12. Ziyodullayeva, M., & Muxtorova, M. (2024). ABDULLA QODIRIY HAYOTI VA IJODIGA AYRIM CHIZGILAR. *NRJ*, 1(3), 860-863.
13. Muxtorova, M. (2024). MAXTUMQULI SHE'RIYATIDA AYTISHUV: AN'ANA VA IZDOSHLIK. *NRJ*, 1(3), 254-257.
14. Tajenova, G., Turdiyeva, G., Qurbanov, A., & Isakov, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *Архив научных исследований*, (14).
15. Janabay, I., Gulbahar, T., Gulayda, T., Alisher, Q., & Ilkhambek, I. (2020). Current state and development of agricultural products exports of the republic of uzbekistan. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(8), 1684-1693.
16. Turdieva, G., Abishov, M., & Muratbaev, I. (2024). THE IMPACT OF CREDIT RISKS ON AN EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION IN THE FINANCIAL SERVICES OF COMMERCIAL BANKS. *NRJ*, 1(4), 215-225.
17. Beglenov, N., & Muratbaev, I. (2023). HOTEL SERVICES AS AN OBJECT OF STRATEGIC MARKETING ORIENTED TO THE CONSUMER. *Science and Education in Karakalpakstan*, 32(2), 175-177.
18. Xalmuratovich, B. S. (2024). JAHON AMALIYOTIDA AGROKLASTER TIZIMINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH VA YURITISH BO 'YICHA TO 'PLANGAN TAJRIBALAR TAHLILI. *Scientific Journal of Actuarial Finance and Accounting*, 4(04), 140-150.
19. Bayjanov, S. X., & Abishov, M. S. (2024). DEVELOPING THE ACTIVITY OF JOINT STOCK COMPANIES BY IMPROVING DIVIDEND POLICY. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(3), 94-97.
20. Sultanov, B., Nurimbetov, T., Bayjanov, S., Seyilbekov, B., & Durmanov, A. (2023, October). Trends in change and the current state of the effectiveness of land reclamation measures in agriculture. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 2921, No. 1). AIP Publishing.

